

**NATIONAL ACTION GAMES OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE THEIR PEDAGOGICAL
AND PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.**

Iroda Oralbaeva

Nukus branch of Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports 2nd year student

Yunus Xojabaev

Nukus branch of Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports 2nd year student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8416178>

Abstract. *The article discusses about the features of the Uzbek national games, the role of these games in the education of children and students, their history, in-depth analysis of scientific views on the widespread application of theoretical psychological knowledge in practice. training of students is carried out. The origins of the games, the work of great scientists in this field, the physical, pedagogical and physiological features of the national outdoor sports games.*

Keywords: *Sports, history, national open games, mental development of children, charisma, physiology, physiological processes of development, direction, strategy, plan.*

**НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПОДВИЖНЫЕ ИГРЫ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА,
ИХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ.**

Аннотация. *В статье рассказывается об особенностях узбекских национальных игр, роли этих игр в воспитании детей и студентов, их истории, углубленном анализе научных взглядов на широкое применение теоретических психологических знаний на практике. проводится обучение студентов. Истоки игр, работы великих ученых в этой области, физические, педагогические и физиологические особенности национальных спортивных игр на открытом воздухе.*

Ключевые слова: *спорт, история, национальные открытые игры, умственное развитие детей, харизма, физиология, физиологические процессы развития, направление, стратегия, план.*

From the day the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, sports and Great attention is paid to the development of national characteristics of physical education. Development of sports and sports culture in the republic, series for sports education laws and presidential decrees were adopted. This is of historical importance decisions have the power of charisma, inspiration - more precisely, they open the door to great achievements.

The goal of the national open games of the Uzbek people is to make the young generation strong and brave is to educate as ancestors, by mastering the external games of the people can be achieved, in addition to this, national games in children, youth can develop and awaken. history, culture of Uzbek national games, a sense of interest and respect for their traditions. Sport creates a healthy environment, every in raising a well-rounded generation and developing spiritual height is the decisive force. We are still developing, we are still important education we have to solve the problems. The emergence of mobile national Uzbek games if we pay attention to its existence and formation, then its roots go back to the distant past, has a long history. The main manifestations of national physical culture are: personal games, scandals, myths, legends, heroic epics, his own expressions are created in dance and music. Material and spiritual left by our ancestors heritage indicates the history of the emergence of folk games. Folk games The history of emergence is the first stage in the development of the historical-archaeological society and the emergence of folk

games in ethnographic sources and we are open to national Uzbek we also find interesting information about the development of sports games.

The description and appearance of these games in the scientific works of our great ancestors a lot of historical information can be given about it. We Uzbek national games a lot of interesting and useful information about it can be found in Mahmud Koshgari's book "Devonu lugatit turk", Abu Ali ibn Sina's "Medical Canon", Kaikovus'

We can find it in "Kabusnama" books. , Amar Khayyam "Navroznama", Yusuf Khos Khajib "Kutat-u bilig", Husaina Vaiz Koshifiy "Fituvvatnomayi Sultani yahud Tariqat of youth", Alisher Navoi "Khamasa", Pirimkul Kodirova "Star nights", Mirmuksina "Timur Malik Such historical, scientific and artistic works, people The history of the game is presented in interesting facts. History of sports games learning, young people, of course, read the books of our great ancestors, with this he not only with the history of the development and emergence of these games, but also with historical, they also get acquainted with scientific and fiction literature. I think it's ours has a great influence on the spiritual and religious development of our youth. Games while studying the history, he gets acquainted with the works of our great ancestors. One in raising a healthy and intelligent generation, as illustrated by several national open games considering the impact of games on physical development and their pedagogical features can exit. Currently, physical education in secondary general education schools in the lessons "Goat and seven children", "Pulling the rope", "Rabbit without a hole", "Quick and national open games such as "clear" are often used. "Goat and seven kids" national open games.

The course of the game: 7-10 students, a goat and seven children participate in the game. Goat stands in the middle of the circle formed by the children. Children holding hands, goat they circle around, one kid runs up and asks for food, the mother goat is patient requires you to be, it's not ready yet. Then another comes running, a goat he says the food is ready and wash the dishes and go to prepare the food.

The boy breaks all the dishes and all the children run away. The goat starts catching the children, he catches the goat first, so the game continues. Pedagogical feature of the game: the game draws the attention of students, develops sensitivity skills. The game improves students' agility, dexterity, develops endurance and coordination of movements. Physiological of the game feature: in children, several muscle groups work at the same time, it is active provides blood circulation, blood flow improves and it works, so that the mother does not catch a goat, makes plans. And the tactics of quickly catching baby goats learns The vitality of the lungs, active attention develops.

"Pull the rope". The game is also a group game. The teacher of each team hangs the ball behind him, the teams line up facing each other; a rope is thrown between them. He was the first to reach the ball with his head the team is considered the winner. The last member of the team pulls behind the team must touch the head of the ball.

Pedagogical feature of the game: the game increases students' attention, teamwork, mutual support, friendship.

Physiological features of the game: the muscular system of the limbs, strength, develops activity, increases the movement of respiratory movements, breathing normalizes the frequency.

A rabbit without a hole. "An active, physical game played with basketball. The game can be held both on the street and in the debate hall. There are several for this students are chosen as

"rabbits" by the teacher with a basketball must comply with the given sports norms, in the second half of the field or the gym has "holes" that can be hoops, hoops, or a balloon from the car.

Students must meet the following standards:

1. Alternately drives the ball to the right or left;
2. Bending and changing direction to drive the ball with a strong shot;
3. Instead, drive the ball around;
4. Driving the ball in a circle along a line;
5. Change direction to drive the ball over the pins in a row.

During the performance of the standard, the teacher shines and with the correct running with the ball orders to reach the ball and take possession of the mink. Did not run straight and hole Anyone who fails to take possession will receive a penalty point. Minimum score who collects is the winner.

Pedagogical feature of the game: the game helps to train attention, courage, intelligence will give. To develop strength, speed, endurance, coordination of movements will help. Physiological feature of the game: develops all muscle groups, active attention, hearing, endurance, coordination of movements, circulation active movements develop the activity of the vestibular apparatus.

Muscles contractions, ankle stiffness, arch support muscles, sports activities improves the speed of tactics.

"Fast and accurate". This active sports game is both basketball and volleyball will be held in the sports hall. The teacher is a circle with a diameter of 2 m draws, one team is formed in the second half of the second group. Ring in the middle there will be two participants, one from both teams. One ball per team given, the participants in turn circle the participant of the opposing team must knock down. Whoever hits him with the ball gets a point, whichever team has more points there is and he wins. Pedagogical feature of the game: the game is dexterity, speed, helps to develop sensitivity, courage, endurance. The game itself feature in movement, running, accuracy, precision. Physiological of the game feature: all muscle groups, tactics, muscle contraction speed, sensation of fingers, blood circulation, active attention, direction, conditional movement develops reflexes. To raise a healthy, moderate, talented generation has both pedagogical and physical and physiological significance, attributes and such national open games without attribution can be counted in great numbers.

REFERENCES

1. Т.С.Усмонхўжаев., А.А.Пулатов., Ш.А.Пулатов., Д.Х.Абдуллаев. «Теория и практика национальных подвижных игр». Ташкент 2014.
2. Каримжон Рахимкулов. «Национальные подвижные игры».изд. «Тафаккур Бустони». Ташкент 2012.
3. Энциклопедический словарь по физической культуре и спорту. Том 3 Гл. ред.- Г. И. Кукушкин. М., Физкультура и спорт.